

Microeconomic Impacts of COVID-19 Pandemic: Case Study of Three Slums in Sylhet City, Bangladesh

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Abstract

The coronavirus outbreak named COVID-19 has disrupted not only the Chinese economy but also globally. It is not only a global pandemic and public health crisis but also it has severely affected the global economy and financial markets. The impacts of COVID-19 viral pandemic become highly personal. Individual experience mental, physical and financial loss. The pandemic has disrupted economic loss globally, nationally and individually. It has shattered lives across all countries and communities. Bangladesh is also not an exception. It's also facing economic crisis due to COVID-19 pandemic. The most vulnerable groups in Bangladesh primarily rely on daily income sources are greatly affected by the pandemic. This study was conducted in three slums of Sylhet city and data were collected from the sample of selected 100 households. A house to house survey was conducted to collect data. The study explored the relationships between respondent's age, family size, monthly income, employment status and number of earning members in the family. 44% people had lost their jobs due to lockdown. Most of them are women engaged with house servant occupation. Income of rickshaw pullers, hawkers and small business (tong) owners has been decreasing day by day during the time of lockdown. The number of men who are engaged with rickshaw pulling occupation are 67%. Among other 33%, 11% were working as waiters at different small local restaurants, 13% were working at shops and markets as salesmen and 9% men were involve with hawking and small businesses. 60% families had 2 earning members but due to the pandemic, 45% families had lost one of their earning member in the family. This study indicates the problems of day laborers in pandemic.

Keywords

Pandemic, COVID-19, infectious disease, lockdown, microeconomics, unemployment.

Introduction

The World has been usurped by a pandemic for almost whole 2020 year. It was identified as a new coronavirus (severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2, or SARS-CoV-2), and later named as COVID-19 (Qiu et al., 2020). The disease COVID-19 was first originated in the city of Wuhan in the Hubei province of China and has spread rapidly across the world. By mid-June, there had been over 8 million cases of COVID-19 globally, with over 436,000 deaths (Brodeur et al., 2020). It not only caused enormous human tragedy but also tremendous economic damage. The economic damage had a great impact on Bangladesh also. Bangladesh is a developing country. A large portion of its people living under poverty line. The most vulnerable groups in Bangladesh rely on daily income sources, and the loss of these income sources were highly effected their lives (NAWG, 2020). Current situation measures have and will continue to severely affect daily wage earners who rely on unsustainable, daily wage earning in order to support themselves and their families. They are mostly vulnerable in terms of living arrangement, food consumption and possessions on wealth, participation in decision making of the family and social attitude and values (Pal & Hussain, 2016). The Government of Bangladesh has delivered significant resources to support these vulnerable communities impacted. However, it is likely that a coordinated humanitarian response over a 12-month period will be needed to supplement these efforts. It will provide the basic future planning including where activities need to be focused, who is the most in need and how the programs can be best exempted (NAWG, 2020).

Objectives of the Study

The overall objective of the study was to know more about the economic impact of COVID19 pandemic on poor people. Therefore, the main objectives of the study were:

- To know the financial status of different households living in the slum areas of Sylhet City.
- To know their current situation and way of livings.

Related Literature Review

Bloom et al. (2005) estimate the potential economic impact of a pandemic by the Oxford economic forecasting model resulting from the mutation of avian influenza strain. They assume a mild pandemic with a 20% attack rate and a 0.5 percent case-fatality rate and a consumption shock of 3%. The scenario includes two-quarters of demand contraction only in Asia (combined effect 2.6% Asian GDP or US\$113.2 billion. Global GDP is reduced by 0.6%, global trade of goods and services contracts by \$2.5 trillion (14%). Open economies are more vulnerable to international shocks.

Hyams et al. (2002) illustrated the impact of COVID19 pandemic in China. Entire cities in China have closed and travel restrictions placed by countries on people entering from infected countries. The fear of an deadly virus is similar in its psychological effects to the reaction to biological and other forms of terrorism threats and causes a high level of stress, often with long-term outcomes.

Boissay and Rungcharoenkitkul, 2020 compared to previous pandemics, COVID-19 has a great impact on the elderly from a health perspective. The lockdown measures, however are not only affect the global economy but also has a massive impact on physical and mental health. This has led to raise financial market turbulence and enlarged the economic shock. Moreover, borrowing and higher debt levels increased among firms, households and especially poor people during this time make the short-term shocks more strong compared to previous pandemics.

Brodeur et al., 2020 did a survey focusing the emerging and rapidly growing literature on the economic consequences of COVID-19 and government response. The paper also synthetize the insights emerging from a very large number of studies. It reviewed different research related to lockdown, social distancing, particularly in regards to its determinants, its effectiveness in extinguishing the spread of COVID-19 and its consent.

Maliszewska et al., 2020 at the time of writing, WHO reported cases of COVID19 in 206 countries and reported deaths are more than 40,000 people. The primary focus is necessarily on containment, treating the ill and helping communities cope with the epidemic. The paper indicates the potential loss of earning in affected countries could be significant, with global GDP declining by up to 3.9%, and developing countries hit the hardest (4% on average, but some over 6.5%). Governments will need to offer sufficient support to affected businesses and households.

Methodology of the Study

The area of SCC is 2650 Square Kilometer having population about 500000. The total numbers of slums in Sylhet City Corporation (SCC) are about 754. Three slums of SCC were selected randomly for collecting the relevant information. This study was based on quantitative research method with various data collection procedures, such as interview, house to house survey, focus group discussion (FGD). To carry out investigations, several questionnaires were prepared and asked to the selected respondents to collect necessary information such as their economical ups and downs, employment status during COVID19 pandemic. The study was based on primary data. The householder constituted the population for this study. Among them 100 households were selected for sample. The sampling procedure was done by selected slums. The included slum areas are: Baluchar Notunbazar, North Baluchar and Fajil Chist. They are known as colony and the name of the colonies of the selected areas are Notunbazar Colony, Uttar Baluchar Colony and Safiq Khan's Colony.

Variable under study

The researcher took adequate care in selecting the variables of the study. The following variables were selected for the study:

The variables of the study were family size, family income (per month), level of education, age and occupation. The descriptions of variables are given bellow:

Family size

Family size of a respondent was measured by the number of his/her family member including himself/herself, children, wife/husband and parents.

Family income (per month)

Family income of the respondent referred to the total monthly earning in TK of the respondent and all family members of a family. It was measured in terms of actual amount of TK.

Level of Education

Educational level of a respondent was measured by the number of years of schooling he or she completed. A respondent did not know how to read and write his/her name the respondent was taken as illiterate. Education level was taken as Primary (1-5), High School (6-10).

Age

The age of a respondent refers to the period of time from his/her birth to the time of interview. It was measured in terms of actual years.

Occupation

The main income source of respondent in per month was assessed as his or her occupation. Occupation 6 categories; hawker, rickshaw puller, waiter, small business owner (tong), maid, salesman.

Data analysis

The data analysis was done using the collected data from questionnaire survey and FGD. For the quantitative data personal judgment, expert's comments, results of the key information interview, public survey and participant's interview was needed for its analysis and interpretation. The recorded interviews and focus group discussions were transcribed in full and the accuracy was checked against the original recording and noted by the researcher. The data was tabulated and relevant statistical tools and computer software were employed for analyzing and interpreting the results. Interview and focus group discussion participants talked about their family status, employment problems, financial crisis and general wellbeing. Some of them were confident to talk about family matters including personal experiences at a job, different difficulties and people's attitude towards them etc.

Results

The findings of the study have been presented in following sections:

Selected characteristics of the household respondents

In the study we have discussed some characteristics of the household respondents such as occupation, family size, family income (monthly), level of education, age. Level of education and monthly income (TK)

From my study areas, total 35.5% respondents were illiterate and rest percentages were literate in different categories which has a positive significance in their occupation. The literacy percentage was higher in case of men than in women.

Based on their monthly income, the respondents were classified into three categories, low income (below 5000Tk), middle income (5001-10,000Tk), high income (10,000Tk).

Table 1: Level of education and family income of slum people

Category		Respondents (%)
Family income	Low income (< 5000 tk)	13.5
	Middle income (5000-10000 tk)	62
	High income (>10,000 tk)	24.5
Total		100%
Level of education	Illiterate	35.5
	Primary (1-5)	43
	High school (6-10)	21.5
Total		100%

Occupation

Among these 100 families, the highest percentage of males are involved with rickshaw pulling occupation about 67%, 13% are engaged with salesmen job and the rest of them are hawker, waiter at different local restaurants, small business owner (tong) etc. In case of females, 44% were unemployed as they had lost their job during the pandemic and the rest of are working as housemaids.

Figure 1: Occupation of slum people

Family size and age

In these 100 families, most of the families were small size 55.5%, 28% had middle family and very few are large family size. Age of the working male and females are around 23-50 years old.

Current Financial Situation of the Respondents

The respondents were currently living a miserable life due to the COVID19 pandemic. During lockdown, most of them were lost their jobs and others facing problem regarding lower income. One of the respondents who is a rickshaw puller stated that:

“The daily income is decreased almost half compared to the pre-pandemic situation. This is not my own rickshaw. So I have to give a fixed amount of money to the owner at the end of day. After giving him the daily rent, there are nothing much left for me to run my family. I am waiting whole day at different point of the city but most of the day no passenger showed in the lockdown.”

The study findings illustrated that, 60% of the families had two earning member in the family but during lockdown 45% of them lost one of their earning members as they had lost their job. One FGD participant, a 65 years old shared his view in the following way:

“I have stopped working two years ago as both my son and my daughter in law were working. But during lockdown, my daughter in law lost her job. She was a housemaid. After she lost her job, it is getting hard for us to live. Sometimes we only eat rice and salt. My son’s income is also decreasing day by day so I have to start working again. But due to lockdown, both of our earnings are not sufficient to run the family.”

The data demonstrate that the respondents suffer extreme poverty due to COVID19.. One 36 years old female participants who lost her job and her husband during pandemic stated that:

"I was working as a housemaid for like 6 years. My husband is a hawker. We were not so poor as both of our incomes were good enough for us to live a normal life. However, when the pandemic situation started, I had lost my jobs and my husband died of corona virus. Both of our income sources suddenly stopped. First few months, we were live on our savings but after that it was a nightmare for us. Then me and my son started collecting waste bottles and sell them to the brokers. But the earning amount is very little. We only get 40-50 TK in a whole day."

Problems Faced during Study

During study, the researcher had faced a lots of problems arising from the people living there. Majority of them were not co-operative. They were unwilling to share their information, personal details or taking pictures. A young man told that:

"We do not agree to tell you anything about us. Many people came our slums telling us that they needed our information to get us help from the Government but till now we do not get any help or anything from anyone. All of you are come here for your self-interest."

Some of them were used abusive language and misbehaved with me thinking me as Government employee and whatsoever.

Conclusion

The people in slum areas face difficulty to meet their daily needs as well as their physiological, psychological and social needs. They are mostly vulnerable in terms of living arrangement, food consumption and possessions on wealth and social values. COVID19 has greatly affected to the people who involved with jobs like house servant and waiter. Most of them have lost their jobs at the time of lockdown. On the other hand, income of rickshaw pullers, hawkers and small business owners have decreased. In the slum areas childrens are more vulnerable due to the extreme poverty. During lockdown, they could not attend online classes as they did not have any kind of smart gadgets. Many of them are started working as child labor because of the extreme poverty. The media should assist by presenting positive images of slum people, particularly emphasizing the need for respect because of their continuing contributions to society. This study was conducted in a very short period of time during COVID-19 lockdown. It could not cover all the slum areas in Sylhet City. It has been suggested that further research should conducted in those areas and different NGOs and Government should take proper steps to release these poor people from their misery.

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Declaration of Conflicting Interests

The authors declared no potential conflicts of interest with respect to the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

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